

Case Study: Impact of Compiler-Version Discrepancies on Contract Behavior

To more clearly demonstrate the potential impact of CVD risks, in this section the risk “Mstore Misoptimization” is rewritten as a more complete number-guessing game and deployed on the Sepolia test network. We then interact with it as game participants to examine whether the contract’s rewards can be successfully obtained. Figure in the end of the document presents the full deployed example contract. Since the risks discussed in this paper arise only under specific compiler versions, the subsequent experiments are conducted with two different version types to compare whether divergent outcomes occur.

In the example contract, a guessing game named **GuessNumberGame** is defined. The dealer sets the target number by invoking the `setTargetNumber` function, where the value is determined through an assembly block: it first reads the `chainid()`, then applies an encryption operation on `block.number`, and finally multiplies the two to obtain the target result. From this process, it can be observed that under normal circumstances (i.e., without the vulnerability), the target number should always be positive. The dealer can also withdraw funds from the contract via the `withdrawFunds` function. Players participate by depositing funds and invoking the `makeGuess` function to choose a number. If the chosen number matches the target, the player receives half of the contract’s balance as a reward; otherwise, the staked amount is added to the pool.

5.3.1 Correct Compiler Version Testing

We selected the Solidity version 0.8.24 as the correct compiler version for testing. The contract was compiled using the online Solidity compiler Remix, then deployed to the Ethereum Sepolia testnet via MetaMask. The deployment was successful, and detailed contract information can be clearly observed through the Ethereum block explorer Etherscan. Figure 1 shows the deployment page, where the compiler version is 0.8.24 with the Solidity optimizer enabled.

Acting as the dealer, we invoked the `setTargetNumber` function to generate the contract’s target number. As shown in Figure 2, the contract’s owner, the `rewardPool`, and the generated `targetNumber` can be observed. The final target number produced was 89240888.


```

1 // SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT
2 pragma solidity ^0.8.0;
3 contract GuessNumberGame {
4     address public owner;
5     uint256 public targetNumber;
6     uint256 public rewardPool;
7     event GuessMade(address indexed player, uint256 guess, bool success);
8     constructor() payable{
9         owner = msg.sender;
10        rewardPool = msg.value;
11    }
12    modifier onlyOwner() {
13        require(msg.sender == owner, "Only the owner can call this function");
14        _;
15    }
16
17    function setTargetNumber() public {
18        uint256 tmpNumber;
19        assembly {
20            let hash := chainid()
21            mstore(0, hash)
22        }
23        uint256 numbers=uint256(keccak256(abi.encodePacked(blockhash(block.number))))%10+1;
24        assembly {
25            let chain := mload(0)
26            tmpNumber := mul(chain, numbers)
27        }
28        targetNumber = tmpNumber;
29    }
30    function makeGuess(uint256 _guess) public payable {
31        require(msg.value > 0.0005 ether, "Must send some ether to make a guess");
32        require(_guess > 0, "Must guess a positive number");
33        rewardPool += msg.value;
34
35        if (_guess == targetNumber) {
36            uint256 reward = rewardPool / 2;
37            rewardPool = rewardPool - reward;
38            payable(msg.sender).transfer(reward);
39            emit GuessMade(msg.sender, _guess, true);
40        } else {
41            emit GuessMade(msg.sender, _guess, false);
42        }
43    }
44    function withdrawFunds(uint256 amount) public onlyOwner {
45        require(amount <= address(this).balance, "Insufficient balance");
46        payable(owner).transfer(amount);
47        rewardPool -= amount;
48    }
49    receive() external payable {
50        rewardPool += msg.value;
51    }
52 }

```